

NOTES

Synthesis of Methyl β -2-(1-methyl-5,6,7,8-Tetrahydronaphthyl) Ethyl Ketone*

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In connection with the studies related to the synthesis of anthrasteroids, we desired methyl β -2-(1-methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydronaphthyl)—ethyl ketone (V) as a key starting material. In the present communication we report the synthesis of the ketone (V).

1-methyl- $\Delta^{1,9}$ -octal-2-one (I)¹, b.p. 125-30°/8mm., was obtained in a satisfactory yield through the condensation of β -chloroethyl ethylketone with ethyl sodiocyclohexanone-2-carboxylate followed by ring closure and hydrolytic decarboxylation with boiling ethanolic potassium hydroxide solution. The ketone (I) was subjected to Reformatsky

*Synthesis of anthrasteroids—Part I.

1. (a) D. K. Banerjee, S. Chatterjee and S. P. Bhattacharyya, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 408.

(b) G. Stork and G. Brinbaum—*Tetrahedron Letters*, 1961, 313.

reaction² with ethyl bromoacetate which yielded the diene ester (II) b.p. 145-50°/2mm., $\lambda_{\max}$ 245 m μ (log ϵ 4.06), through dehydration of the intermediate tertiary alcohol during its isolation. (Found: C, 76.79; H, 9.22. C₁₅H₂₂O₂ requires C, 76.93; H, 9.40 per cent).

The diene ester (II) underwent smooth dehydrogenation³ on heating with calculated quantity of sulphur at 240-60° for 2 hr. and yielded the tetralin ester (IIIb), b.p. 145-50°/3mm., which showed the expected ultraviolet absorption maxima at 267 m μ (log ϵ 3.23) and 337 m μ (log ϵ 2.41) characteristic of the substituted tetralin chromophore. (Found: C, 77.05; H, 8.41. C₁₅H₂₀O₂ requires C, 77.60; H, 8.62 per cent).

The corresponding acid (IIIa) was obtained as a crystalline solid, m.p. 128-29° on recrystallisation from ether-petroleum ether. (Found: C, 76.33; H, 7.77. C₁₃H₁₆O₂ requires C, 76.47; H, 7.84 per cent).

The alcohol (IVa), b.p. 140°-45°/0.7 mm. (Found: C, 81.92; H, 9.27. C₁₃H₁₈O requires C, 82.10; H, 9.47 per cent), obtained through reduction of the ester (IIIb) with lithium aluminium hydride, was converted to the bromide (IVb), b.p. 170-75°/4-5 mm., with phosphorus tribromide. Initial attempts at the conversion of the bromide (IV b) to the nitrile (IVc) by boiling with aqueous ethanolic potassium cyanide solution was not promising, most of the bromide being recovered unchanged. However, the desired conversion was achieved in an excellent yield by carrying the displacement reaction of the bromide (IV b) with potassium cyanide in dimethyl formamide at steam-bath temperature. The nitrile (IVc), b.p. 175-80°/3mm., was converted to the methyl ketone (V), b.p. 135-40°/0.4 mm., through condensation with methyl magnesium iodide in boiling benzene followed by acidic hydrolysis of the intermediate complex. (Found: C, 82.97; H, 9.01. C₁₅H₂₀O requires C, 83.33; H, 9.26 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* of the ketone (V) prepared in the usual way on recrystallisation from dilute methanol melted at 208-209°. (Found: C, 70.10; H, 8.17. C₁₆H₂₃N₃O requires C, 70.33; H, 8.42 per cent).

The conversion of the aforementioned ketone (V) to the anthrasteroid (VI) and related derivatives following the "benzhydryndane approach" of steroid synthesis⁴ will be reported in a separate communication.

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3. J. C. Bardhan and D. Nasipuri, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 350.
4. D. K. Banerjee, H. N. Khastagir, J. Dutta, E. J. Jacob, N. S. Johnson, C. F. Allen, B. K. Bhattacharyya, J. C. Collins (Jr), A. L. Mc Closkey, W. T. Tsatsos, W. A. Verdenburgh, K. L. Williamson—*Tetrahedron Letters*, 1961, 77.